

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: MARAFa****FIRST NAME: HAMZA****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA 401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR GULMA**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author uses Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author uses Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 3%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA 401D

1. One of the following is not among the five general aims of research projects;

- Ask a question worth answering
- Find an answer that you can support with good reasons
- Find good data that you can use as reliable evidence to support your reasons
- Find an answer to the world's problem¹**

2. In academic research, a problem is defined as;

- Something we try to avoid
- Something we seek out or even invent²**
- A mistake worth exploring
- Something imposes on us by nature

¹ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations; Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Ninth Ed. (Chicago: University Press, 2018) 23.

² Ibid., 29.

3. One of the following statements is an incorrect reason for citing your sources in academic research;
- To give credit to the authors
 - To help readers expand their library³**
 - To reassure readers about the accuracy of your facts
 - To show readers the research tradition that informs your work
4. According to the EU style of reference;
- All footnotes end with a semicolon, except those consisting solely of internet or email address
 - All footnotes end with a full stop, except those consisting solely of the internet or email address⁴**
 - All footnotes end with a comma, except those consisting solely of internet or email address
 - All footnotes end with a colon, except those consisting solely of the internet or email address
5. One of the following is incorrect about citation management tools;
- It enables researchers to keep track of data source
 - It enables researchers to double-check data sources
 - It enables researchers to compile a list of sources consulted
 - It enables researchers to double-check the spelling⁵**

³. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers*, 23.

⁴. European Commission, *English Style Guide: A Handbook of Authors and Translators in the European Commission*. Eighth Ed. (Brussels: European Commission, 2021) 7.

⁵. Linda D. Bloomberg and Volpe F. Marie, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation; A Roadmap from Beginning to End*. Fourth Ed. (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2019), 77-202.

6. All but one of the following are attributes of the review of literature;
- Reviews primary sources that are most recent empirical studies from scholarly journals and publications, as well as secondary sources
 - States up front the bodies of literature that will be covered and why
 - Synthesizes findings across studies and compares and contrasts different research outcomes, perspectives, or methods
 - Write your research finding with notes and recommendations**⁶
7. One of the following is not a definition of Qualitative research;
- It is a field that crosscuts disciplines and subject matters
 - It includes traditions associated with foundationalism, positivism and post-positivism
 - It is connected to cultural and interpretive studies through many perspectives and methods
 - It derives research inferences from the quantitative world**⁷
8. Case study methodology could be categorized into all but one of the following;
- exploratory
 - Descriptive
 - Instrumental
 - Reactive**⁸
9. A research proposal is a well-thought-out written action plan that identifies;
- a broad and ambiguous problem statement;

⁶ Linda D. Bloomberg and Volpe F. Marie, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 78.

⁷ Ibid., 143.

⁸ Ibid., 145.

- a purpose statement that describes how the problem will be addressed**⁹
- Research questions that are not tied to the purpose and, when answered
- Review of the literature and relevant research to determine the research impact

10. Plagiarism could be defined as a situation where a researcher;

- Uses and cite all source of information consulted
- Take someone else words or ideas and give them credit
- Take someone else ideas and words without giving credit to the authors**¹⁰
- Consulted different sources and listed them in the reference

⁹. Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/401D Course pack: Period 1*. Fourth Ed. (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 159.

¹⁰. *Ibid.*, 202.

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